

Lunar Lander

Project 1.6

Abstract

This report describes the research, computer implementation and results of group 5 on project 1.6, all shortly described in the following brief overview.

The main tasks of this project were to build a computer application that could be used to calculate a spaceship moving in two directions, let this vessel land and from there, experiment with it to solve specific cases.

The approach proposed by group 5 was to establish a schedule, then split the problem into three parts on which different group members researched intensively before combining their results to implement the actual product.

The novelty in group 5's approach is that a refined combination of existing solutions was used.

The results of the experiments show that different variables such as, the algorithm or the available time influence greatly the given solutions.

The main tasks have all somewhat been solved. The application that could be used to solve the two-dimensional problems was created.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Problem Definition

Main task

The goal of this project was to program a spaceship to land on the moon. This goal had to be achieved in 2 phases.

General tasks

In phase 1, the goal was to complete the following tasks:

1. Write a program which simulates the motion of a spaceship in two dimensions. The spaceship must contain one main thruster for acceleration, and 4 four smaller side thrusters for the rotation. The motion of the spaceship has to be described with the use of differential equations,
2. The output of the program had to be made visible with graphs plotting the calculated data and by animation of the movement of the spaceship.

In phase two, the goal was to:

1. Expand our program with a landing path, located at a given coordinate. In order to achieve a safe landing, some landing conditions should be met.
2. Try to minimize the cost of the flight, by minimizing the time and fuel needed for the spacecraft to land.
3. Try to solve one or more of the additional tasks given.

1.2 Existing Solutions

Although some research has been performed in this direction, we weren't able to find any existing solutions.

1.3 Outline of the report

First, this report will describe in detail the main approaches, methods and algorithms used. Then it will describe in some detail the Java implementation of the application followed by the experiments performed with the application and the results will be presented. In addition the results of these experiments will be discussed. Finally, a conclusion will be made based on the results and their discussion.

2. Approaches, Methods and Algorithms

Our approach consists of two focal points. The first is differential equations, which are used in this project in order to appropriately calculate the movement of the spacecraft. The second is Controllers. These controllers will tell our spacecraft what to do, in order to land safely.

2.1 Differential Equations

To have the spacecraft move correctly through its environment we need to find a mathematical way to describe its change of position based on the forces that are applied to it. The most accurate way to do this, uses differentials and derivatives. Since various differentials, derivatives, and functions become inevitably related to each other via equations, a differential equation (ODE) is the result, governing dynamical phenomena, evolution and variation. Often, quantities are defined as the rate of change of other quantities (time derivatives), or gradients of quantities, which is how they enter differential equations.

After some research online and with the aid of our teachers and tutors we decided to start with the three most known differential equation solvers:

The Euler's method

The Midpoint method, and

The Runge-Kutta method.

In order to proceed with our work we had to find out how they work, how accurate they are and which would be the most suitable in our problem. In this part we will focus on the theory of each method and its expected performance. More details on how we implemented them and how good they performed will be presented in the implementation and in the experiment part of the presentation.

2.1.1 Euler's Method

The Euler method (named after Leonard Euler) is a first-order numerical procedure for solving ordinary differential equations (ODEs) with a given initial value. It is the most basic method for numerical integration and the simplest.

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(t_n, y_n).$$

Figure 2.: Euler's Method Formula

This method is a first-order method, which translates to a local error proportional to the step size.

Figure 3.: Illustration of the Euler method. The unknown curve is in blue, and its polygonal approximation is in red.

We knew that this method was not going to give us accurate approximations but we needed a base case to compare our result, and this was the one.

2.1.2 Midpoint Method

The midpoint method, also known as the “modified Euler method”, is a refinement of the Euler’s method. It is a one-step method and it is given by the formula:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + hf \left(t_n + \frac{h}{2}, y_n + \frac{h}{2}f(t_n, y_n) \right)$$

Figure 4.: for $n=0,1,2,\dots$, h is the step size, t is the time

The function f is being evaluated at $t = t_n + h/2$, which is the midpoint between the known value at t_n and the value that needs to be found at t_{n+1} .

Figure 5.: The red line is the approximation of the tangent line (green) at the midpoint

The local error at each step of this method is of the order of $O(h^3)$, giving a global error of the order of $O(h^2)$ and although it makes more function evaluations than the Euler method, it gives more accurate results.

2.1.3 Runge-Kutta Method

The method we used from the family of Runge-Kutta methods is the one referred to as “classical Runge-Kutta method” or simply as “RK4”. This method approximates the value at y_{n+1} with the use of four increments. Each increment is the product of the size of the interval h and an estimated slope.

- k_1 is the increment based on the slope at the beginning of the interval, using y_n , (from Euler’s method);
- k_2 is the increment based on the slope at the midpoint of the interval, using $y_n + \frac{1}{2}k_1$;
- k_3 is again the increment based on the slope at the midpoint, but now using $y_n + \frac{1}{2}k_2$;
- k_4 is the increment based on the slope at the end of the interval, using $y_n + k_3$.

Those increments are weighted and their average is added to the present value.

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + \frac{1}{6} (k_1 + 2k_2 + 2k_3 + k_4)$$

$$t_{n+1} = t_n + h$$

Figure 6.: Equation of the RK4 method

$$k_1 = hf(t_n, y_n),$$

$$k_2 = hf(t_n + \frac{1}{2}h, y_n + \frac{1}{2}k_1),$$

$$k_3 = hf(t_n + \frac{1}{2}h, y_n + \frac{1}{2}k_2),$$

$$k_4 = hf(t_n + h, y_n + k_3).$$

Figure 7.: the four increments used for the approximation.

The RK4 method is a fourth-order method. Its error per step is on the order of h^5 and the total accumulated error is of the order of h^4 . This method gave us the best approximations and is the one that we used for the next part of our problem.

2.2 Controllers

After choosing the best differential equation for the problem at hand, we had to find a suitable controller for our dynamic system that would manipulate the inputs of the system to obtain the desired effect (land safely).

2.2.1 Open loop Controller

The first type of controller that we tried is an open loop controller (also known as *non-feedback controller*). It makes all the computations for its inputs into the system using only the initial state of the system. As a controller, it is simple and has a low computational resource demand. This makes it the ideal controller in a system where feedback is not critical or in a well-defined system where relations between the input and the resulting state can be modeled by a mathematical formula.

Figure 8.: An open loop controller scheme

2.2.2 Closed loop Controller

The other type of controller we used is a closed loop controller (also known as a feedback controller). This controller has access to the state of the system and can use variables of this state as feedback in order to adjust the output as appropriate. This type of controller is more suitable for a dynamic environment where outside factors (disturbances) can change the system.

However, feedback controllers usually result in intermediate periods where the controlled variables are not at the desired set-points, since it has to be off target in order to make some adjustments.

Figure 9.: A closed loop controller scheme

3. Implementation

3.1 Differential equations and solvers

The main part of our algorithm was used throughout the two stages of the project. We started by storing all the data needed for the computations as well as the status of the craft in vectors. We did that for two main reasons: accuracy and performance. The data needed were the three coordinates (x-axis, y-axis and rotation) and their corresponding velocities (x, y and theta). We also used a secondary vector on which we stored the U and V functions. Then a timer was set to give us the time variable needed, and we set the step size h to be equal to 0.1s. We chose 0.1s for the ease of computations. We set up a user friendly interface which allowed the user to input function for the main and the side thrusters. For the functions being inputted by the user we build a “function solver” which evaluates the give string/function at each time-step.

The main program then uses the selected solving method (Euler’s, midpoint or Runge-Kutta) and inputs the numbers stored in the two vectors into the selected formula in order to update the crafts state. Then, a timer allows for the repetition of this procedure. After each function evaluation the information stored in the two vectors is passed to the graphics class which is making everything visual in real time. In addition, graphs displaying the change in variables over time were displayed in matlab.

3.2 Controllers

For the second part of the project we had to implement two types of controllers in order to land the spacecraft. In order to achieve that we added two classes to our software (one for each controller type).

Figure 10.: A simplified UML diagram of the implemented controller

3.2.1 Open loop controller

While implementing open loop controllers, we first created sub goals that would create a path for us which at the end would take us to landing pad. Assuming a landing position of

(0,0), our first sub goal was to reach point $x=0$ with $V_x=0$. In order to achieve this, we first rotate our spacecraft 45 degrees to the horizontal. Then we move with constant acceleration to the left and before reaching $x=0$, we rotate 90 degrees to the right in order to halt our x velocity. When the craft has finished an x velocity of 0 the craft is rotated to 0 radians from the vertical (straight up) and then the second sub goal of vertically landing can be achieved. The following part will explain in detail how this was achieved.

1. Rotations:

For rotations we chose to use the maximum thrust that we could use, because it will be time efficient. As in open loop controllers everything is pre planned; we had to find a formula for the time needed to perform these rotations. Below equations describe how to find it :

$$V_{\theta}(t) = V_{\theta}(0) + \dot{V}(t) * t \quad (1)$$

$$\theta(t) = \theta(0) + V_{\theta}(0) * t + \dot{V}(t) * \frac{t^2}{2} \quad (2)$$

Figure 11.: Equations describing how to find the rotations

The main goal in rotation is to rotate the spacecraft, but also stop rotating when the goal is reached. In order to achieve it, we divide our interval into two. In the first interval we give thrust/acceleration that starts to rotate spacecraft in desired direction. In the second interval we apply *opposite* thrust, which allows the spacecraft reach the desired goal, but also stop it. Afterwards, rotational thrust is switched off. So, from equations (1) and (2) we can find the time needed to rotate spacecraft *half way* and then apply opposite force for same amount of time. Time needed for half rotations is found in following way :

$$\Delta\theta = \theta(t) - \theta(0) = \text{desired Angle} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\Delta\theta}{2} = V_{\theta}(0) * t + \dot{V}(t) * \frac{t^2}{2} \quad (4)$$

Figure 12.: Equations describing how to find time needed for rotation

For all rotations, because of the mirrored nature of this rotational function, the initial angular velocity must be $V_{\theta}(0) = 0$, otherwise the absolute value of the angular velocity after the rotation is complete would be greater than 0. ($|V_{\theta}(n)| > 0$) So, if we plug in this value into equation (3), we will get :

$$\frac{\Delta\theta}{2} = \dot{V}(t) * \frac{t^2}{2} \quad (5)$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta\theta}{\dot{V}(t)}} \quad (6)$$

Figure 13.: Result

Equation (6) shows, how much time is needed to rotate half way through the desired angle. By applying force during that time and then applying opposite force for same amount of time, we are reach our desired angle and angular velocity equal to zero, which means, it stops rotating after reaching goal rotational angle.

2. Blocking V_x and V_y velocities.

In order to bring the x and y velocities to 0 we use different stepwise functions, both while rotating and not rotating. For the first sub-goal, when we rotate our spacecraft to the direction of the landing pad (i.e. point to where $x=0$), we set our main thrusters so that we will not drop (i.e V_y will be 0 or very small), but still be able to go in the direction of the landing pad. Afterwards, when we rotate backwards in order to stop, we have to oppose V_x such that both velocity and coordinate of x-axis will be zero. Then, in third and last part we perform a vertical landing, which decreases V_y that we gained through free falling. Below formulas explains these steps :

$$\ddot{y} = u(t) * \cos(\theta(t)) - 1.63 \quad (7)$$

Figure 14.: An explanation of the steps taken.

Equation (7) shows the behaviour of acceleration in y axis. By using this information, we can find the appropriate thrust to counter V_y :

$$\begin{aligned} V_y(0) &= 0 \\ V_y(t) &= V_y(0) + \dot{y}(t) * t \\ V_y(t) &= \dot{y}(t) * t \end{aligned}$$

Figure 15.: The appropriate thrust to counter V_y .

As we start our movement and begin to rotate, our initial velocity will be zero. In order to counter our Y velocity and stop the spacecraft from dropping, we have to make our

$V_y(t) = 0$. In order to achieve this goal we use the equation below for our main thrust :

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_y(t) &= 0 \\
 \dot{y}(t) * t &= 0 \\
 (u(t) * \cos(\theta(t)) - 1.63) * t &= 0 \\
 u(t) * \cos(\theta(t)) - 1.63 &= 0 \\
 u(t) &= \frac{1.63}{\cos(\theta(t))} \quad (8)
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 16.: Equation for the main thrust.

By using the formula derived above, we can counter our V_y and still move in direction of x- axis. This thrust is used while we reach the point where we have to start opposing V_x . This is performed by rotating the spacecraft 90 degrees to the opposite direction that it rotated first. In order to achieve it, the following formulas are used :

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_x(t) &= V_x(0) + a * t \quad (9) \\
 x(t) &= x(0) + V_x(0) * t + a * \frac{t^2}{2} \quad (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 17.: Formulas used for rotating the spacecraft.

In order to achieve our goal described above, we have to find appropriate t and a values, such that both (3) and (4) will be equal to zero.

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_x(t) &= 0 \\
 x(t) &= 0 \\
 V_0(t) + a * t &= 0 \quad (11) \\
 x(0) + V_0(t) * t + a * \frac{t^2}{2} &= 0 \quad (12)
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 18.: Finding appropriate t and values.

Equations (11) and (12) are essential for finding the required values. At that moment, we can use our state vector to read values $V_0(t)$ and $x(0)$. By using them, we can substitute the t we will get from (11), to find a in (12). So, in terms of equations :

$$\begin{aligned}
 t &= -\frac{V_0(t)}{a} \quad (13) \\
 x(0) - \frac{V_0(t)^2}{a} + \frac{V_0(t)^2}{2 * a} &= 0 \quad (14)
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 19.: Substitution of formulas 11 and 12.

By finding out what t has to be in (11), we substituted it by its expression in (12) and got to equation (14).

$$x(0) - \frac{V_0(t)^2}{2 * a} = 0$$

$$a = \frac{V_0(t)^2}{2 * x(0)} \quad (15)$$

Figure 20.: Resulting expression

Equation (15) shows what our acceleration has to be for amount of time t . The time needed can be found by substituting a in (13):

$$t = \frac{2 * x(0)}{V_0(t)} \quad (16)$$

Figure 21.: Resulting expression

To find what our main thrusters force has to be, we can use information from (15):

$$a = u(t) * \sin(\theta(t))$$

$$u(t) = \frac{V_0(t)^2}{2 * x(0) * \sin(\theta(t))} \quad (17)$$

Figure 22.: The force of the main thrusters.

Equations (16) and (17) expresses how thrusters has to work and for how long. After this operation is done, the spacecraft is rotated into its straight position and it is ready for vertical landing.

3. In the third and final part, we try to land our spacecraft vertically from a given y position and V_y . In order to do this, we let spacecraft free fall quarter of the way it has to go and then we try to stop it before it reaches point $(0,0)$. So, first we have to find time needed for free falling:

$$\Delta y = y(0) - y(t) = \frac{1}{4} * y(0) = \textit{displacement}$$

$$\frac{1}{4} * y(0) = V_y(0) * t + a * \frac{t^2}{2} \quad (18)$$

Figure 23.: Time needed for free falling.

Equation (18) shows how to find the time needed in order to free fall in the first quarter of the vertical landing interval. Again, we can use our state vector inside of the craft, in

order to determine values of $\dot{y}(0)$ and $V_y(0)$. Furthermore, in free falling $a=1.63$, because no thrust is applied and $\ddot{y} = 0 * \cos(\theta(t)) - 1.63$. Using this information, we can find out, what time is required:

$$\frac{1.63}{2} * t^2 + V_y(0) * t - \frac{1}{4} * y(0) = 0 \quad (19)$$

Figure 24.: Required time for free falling.

By applying the determinant rule to (19), we can obtain following result:

$$t = \frac{-V_y(0) + \sqrt{V_y(0)^2 - 4 * \frac{1.63}{2} * \left(-\frac{1}{4} * y(0)\right)}}{1.63} \quad (20)$$

Figure 25.: Result by applying the determinant rule.

Equation (20) shows how much time the spacecraft needs for free falling.

The very last operation of the controller is done when free falling is finished. This part tries to stop the spacecraft at landing pad. To do so, it applies constant force in remaining part, which would make $V_y(t) = 0$ when the landing pad is reached. So, our conditions will be: $y(t)=0$ and $V_y(t) = 0$. Using this information, following equations could be obtained:

$$V_y(t) = V_y(0) + a * t = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$y(t) = y(0) + V_y(0) * t + a * \frac{t^2}{2} = 0 \quad (22)$$

Figure 26.: Obtained equation.

In order to obtain values and $V_y(0)$ and $y(0)$, the state vector is used. Next step, would be to find appropriate t and a values. To do so, we substitute t by $\frac{V_y(0)}{a}$ by using equation (21). The following formulas are obtained:

$$t = -\frac{V_y(0)}{a}$$

$$y(0) - \frac{V_y(0)^2}{a} + \frac{V_y(0)^2}{2 * a} = 0 \quad (23)$$

Figure 27.: Obtained formula by substitution.

By performing algebraic manipulations on (23), we can find the following expression for our acceleration:

$$a = \frac{V_y(0)^2}{2 * y(0)} \quad (24)$$

Figure 28.: Expression for acceleration

Equation (24), shows us what final acceleration has to be in order to land safely. We can use the fact that our spacecraft is vertical in order to obtain $u(t)$:

$$a = u(t) * \cos(\theta(t)) - 1.63$$

$$u(t) * \cos(\theta(t)) - 1.63 = \frac{V_y(0)^2}{2 * y(0)}$$

$$\theta(t) = 0 \text{ (vertical landing)}$$

$$u(t) = \frac{V_y(0)^2}{2 * y(0)} + 1.63 \quad (25)$$

Figure 29.: Vertical landing

Equation (25) shows what function has to be used for the main thrusters in order to land safely.

4. Moving up if y is very small.

One of the special cases for open loop controller is, when initial y position is too small to perform actions and land safely. In that case, we move our spacecraft vertically up and then perform the same actions that are explained in previous subchapters. In order to move spacecraft vertically up, we divide our movement into two parts: accelerating and decelerating. In first half, we accelerate our spacecraft by twice of the gravity and then in second half we turn main thrusters off, which as a result, moves spacecraft upwards and then spacecraft becomes steady. To obtain the actual time needed for this we first have to determine to which point we want move. We have chosen y coordinate of 40, as our checkpoint. From this coordinate, our spacecraft will be able to land safely. After choosing this checkpoint, we use the given equations in order to determine time needed. This process is done as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{y} &= u(t) * \cos(\theta(t)) - 1.63 \\ \ddot{y} &= 1.63 = a \\ y(t) &= 40 \\ &\text{(from condition as we want to accelerate first half and decelerate second)} \\ u(t) &= \frac{3.26}{\cos(\theta(t))} \quad (26) \\ \Delta y &= y(t) - y(0) \\ \frac{\Delta y}{2} &= V_y(0) * t + 1.63 * \frac{t^2}{2} \\ V_y(0) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

(because, movement starts stationary and moving up is first movement that is done if needed)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta y}{2} &= 1.63 * \frac{t^2}{2} \\ t &= \sqrt{\frac{\Delta y}{1.63}} \quad (27) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 30.: The process

Equation (27) shows for how long the main thruster has to work and (26) shows what the thrust has to be in that interval. After this the thrust is switched off in order to stop spacecraft at the desired checkpoint (i.e $y=40$).

In conclusion, open loop controller first checks if it is at suitable position to start, if not it moves to suitable position and then performs the series of actions described above.

3.2.2 Closed loop controller

The closed loop Controller in practice is very similar to the Open Loop Controller. It is given the crafts initial state and makes some decisions based on this, using time parameters. For example, if the x-coordinate of the goal is larger than the x-coordinate of the initial position then the craft will rotate right and thrust. If the goal x-coordinate is less than that of the original position it will rotate left and thrust and if they are equal it will begin descent.

At certain points in the crafts path, it uses it's current position and velocity to make decisions on when and how it should perform it's next action. This is the principle of a Closed Loop Controller. A series of methods have been designed in order to perform the necessary actions (rotateTo, fall etc). Further methods can be designed and then utilised into the system.

Below is a diagram of a typical landing path using the closed-loop controller. It is followed by a description of each key point in it's path.

Figure 31.: A typical flight path using the Closed-Loop Controller

1. In it's initial position, the Controller stores many values for frequent use such as the x-distance and y-distance from the goal. It then determines whether it should move left, right or down by taking the sign of the goal subtracted by the starting position. In Java (`Math.signum(goalX – startX)`). It then uses a method to rotate through `thita`, while applying a thrust of $1.67/\cos(\text{thita})$. This keeps the craft from falling or rising while rotating to `thita`. Figure 12 illustrates this.

Figure 32.: The craft in its initial position

2. After a certain amount of time (and therefore a certain amount of thrust has been applied) the craft rotates back round to 0 (from the vertical). Once this operation is complete it saves the distance it has traveled during the path so far (`thrustDistance`).
3. At this point the craft remains upright and traveling at a constant x-velocity.
4. At distance (`thrustDistance`) from the goal x-coordinate, the opposite thrust function is applied (rotate to negative `thita`, thrust and rotate back).
5. Here the controller can make small alterations to the craft in order to position it correctly and ensure it is not moving. The controller then calculates the height from the goal and using this and the specified `Umax` function it drops, applying `Umax` at the appropriate height.

6. The height at which u_{Max} is applied is calculated as follows. $ThrustHeight = (height / (u_{Max}/1.63))$. The diagram below illustrates an example of the relationship between the height and u_{Max} . This method of traversing each axis in turn may not be the most efficient means of reaching a goal, however it allows for the safe landing from any coordinates. In a practical sense, safety is paramount in the landing of such a module. Further research should be done into the cost benefit analysis of such a system and then in future a more efficient means of landing could be implemented.

Figure 33.: A diagram of u_{Max}

In order to stop the craft, the controller takes a ratio of the height to a ratio of u_{Max} and 1.63. This is the height at which U_{max} is applied. Essentially it applies u_{Max} such that it stops at the goal with minimum velocity.

7. At this point the craft has reached it's goal. A check is performed to ensure it's final state meets the requirements stated in the requirements and then determines the landing a success or failure.

Figure 14 and 15 show the implementation of the Closed-Loop Controller.

Figure 34.: A UML diagram showing the implementation of the closed-loop controller.

Figure 35.: A UML diagram showing the implementation of the closed-loop controller.

4. Experiments

4.1 Controllers

For the controllers, we are interested in the total time needed to land the spaceship and whether it landed successfully. We use the same input variables for the open loop controller as well as the closed loop controller, in order to display the results between them.

4.1.1 Open-loop Controller

$x(0)$	$y(0)$	$\theta(0)$	$x(t)$	$\Theta(t)$	$V_x(t)$	$V_y(t)$	$V_\theta(t)$	Time needed (sec)	Landed successfully	u-max	v-max
100	200	0	-28.697	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$1.25 \cdot 10^{-16}$	0.0416	$5.28 \cdot 10^{-17}$	31.6	no	30	$\pi/9$
100	200	0	-9.518	$4.07 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$2.11 \cdot 10^{-15}$	0.015	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-16}$	41.8	no	30	4 rad
110	220	0	-17.944	$3.33 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$2.893 \cdot 10^{-15}$	0.009	$5.28 \cdot 10^{-17}$	36.6	no	30	$\pi/9$
260	300	0	0.0100019	$6.2 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-16}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.2 \cdot 10^{-17}$	63.5	yes	30	$\pi/9$

In the first three test cases the lunar lander crashes. This is because the horizontal distance is too small to get the spaceship to rotate towards the landing path, and back to an angle of 0 degrees. The spaceship will end at the left of the landing path and will crash.

4.1.2 Closed loop Controller

The closed loop controller uses the same methods as the open-loop controller. Because we have a stable environment, the results of the two controllers are exactly the same. Because of a shortage in time we weren't able to implement environmental variables such as the gravity of the moon. We neither had the time to introduce unforeseen landing areas such as a cave. With new unforeseen forces acting on the spaceship, the difference between the controllers could be shown. The closed loop controller is expected to outperform the open loop controller since the latter doesn't take external forces into account.

5. Discussion

5.1 Conclusion

After finishing our experiments, we came to conclusion that our software, although it is functional, it is not complete. We are able to land spacecraft, but not always. The issue we are facing is focused on the inability of the craft to perform some adjustments on x axis. This results in reaching the landing target, but being off centre. The landing conditions are met in the majority of our test cases, but our spacecraft crashes sometimes because of the problem with adjustments on x-axis.

Apart from that, the performance of our software is stable and the results are satisfying.

5.2 Discussions- Practical Applications/Future Work

This problem relates specifically to the real world problem of lunar landing. This program therefore acts as a simulator for such an environment with some obvious limitations.

Firstly, our program simulates just two spatial dimensions. If this program were to be used to accurately model the movement of a real-world craft, it should be able to move in three dimensions. Secondly, our program does not account for more specific values of the craft. Its centre of mass for example, would not necessarily be at the centre of the craft and therefore the rotational thrusters would not necessarily rotate the craft perfectly around its axis. The craft would also lose mass. As fuel is burned in order to land, its mass would decrease and therefore any force the thrusters apply would have a greater effect on its movement. In order to increase the efficiency of the controllers, a new controller based on projectile motion theory could be implemented and added. As in projectile motion thrust is used only in the beginning of flight, it will be fuel efficient.

With further research such factors could be taken into account in order to achieve a more accurate simulation of Lunar Landing. Additional tasks could also be used in order to appropriately test the validity of the Closed-Loop controller. When landing on the earth for example, not only must the Controller account for stronger gravity (9.81m/s^2) but wind must also be accounted for. An Open-Loop Controller would be able to account for wind if it remained constant or could be predicted however in practice this would not be possible. A Closed-Loop Controller could use meteorological data in order to appropriately adjust its behaviour.

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